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Prevalence And Determinants Of Risky Sexual Behaviour Among Students In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers East Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the prevalence and determinants of risky sexual behaviour among students in public secondary school in Rivers East Senatorial District. The study adopted the descriptive cross sectional survey design. The population of the study comprised of all the public senior secondary schools in Rivers East Senatorial District, while the sample size was 1229 students derived using proportionate formula and data obtained using a multistage sampling technique with three stages. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: Prevalence and Determinants of Risky Sexual Behaviours among Students (QPDRSBS) with reliability co-efficient of 0.79. The data collected were analysed using the Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS), descriptive statistics of frequency, simple percentages, mean, and standard deviation were used for answering research questions, and regression model for the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was low (21.1%). The result tested hypotheses revealed that there was a significant relationship between peer pressure (X^2 value = 157.223; df =1; $p < 0.05$), sexual orientation (X^2 value = 760.127; df =1; $p < 0.05$), parent's socioeconomic status (X^2 value = 164.558; df =3; $p < 0.05$) and belief system (X^2 value = 75.366; df =2; $p < 0.05$) and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. It was concluded that there was low prevalence of risky sexual behaviour and factors that determine risky sexual behaviour included, peer pressure, internet usage, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status of parents and religion. It was recommended that the government through the Ministry of Education should implement a comprehensive sex education curriculum that covers topics such as reproductive health, contraception, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and consent.

Keywords: risky sexual behaviour, students, senior secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

Young people are now at increased risk of unsafe sexual behavior and its attendant health problems such as unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections. The progressively increasing rate of sexual activities among adolescents in the past few decades has become a public health concern worldwide (WHO, 2009). The existing cases of risky sexual behaviour are rapidly on the increase ranging from among adolescents over the decades. World Health Organization (WHO) reported that the prevalence of

premarital sexual activity among adolescents varies across regions. According to Aliza et al., (2017), a good proportion of adolescents 45 to 52 percent of sub-Saharan African especially female had sexual intercourse by age 19, also in other developed countries, the prevalence was higher where most young women have had sex prior to age 20.

In Nigeria, studies of Nwigwe and Agbapuonwu (2023) reported that the good proportion of students/adolescents (97.3%) participated in risky sexual behaviours such as engaged in smooching, having multiple sexual partners, watching pornographic videos, touching of sexual organs among others. Eze et al., (2021) further affirmed that that risky sexual behaviour is a consistent among adolescent and students in secondary schools and good proportion of them had boyfriends/girlfriends, been pressurized to have sex by others, going for clubbing/night party and prefer using drugs. Furthermore, Addis et al., (2022) identified that over 50% of students in secondary schools had engaged in risky sexual behaviour and experienced sexual intercourse which was based on the use of internet, watching online sex videos among others. Noor (2017) added that in Malaysia, the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour was 7.0% and 8.8% occurs among adolescents, 5.8% among female students while over 36% had early sexual debut before age 14.

Sexual experimentation and concerns with sexuality that typically arise during adolescence influence how physically and psychologically an adolescent will develop. According to Kar et al. (2015), the physical growth, psychological as well as cognitive development reaches its peak during adolescence while Sales et al. (2013) noted that adolescent sexuality development can be better explained with the bio-psycho-social model. The emergence of sexuality in adolescents is influenced by a combination of biological, psychological, and social variables. Adolescents explore about different appropriate ways to express the love and intimacy (Ott, 2010). The period of adolescence is when a person's thought, perception, and response become sexually flavoured. Adolescent sexual curiosity led to exposure to pornography, indulgence in sexual behaviour, and an increased risk of sexual abuse. During adolescence, an individual's need for intimacy and love making with opposite gender increases.

Risky sexual behaviour puts adolescents at risk for sexually transmitted infections (STIs), unintended pregnancies, and being in a sexual connection before they are old enough to understand what constitutes a healthy relationship. On the other hand, risky sexual behavior refers to any sexual activity that raises the possibility of getting HIV, AIDs, or other STIs, as well as the possibility of getting pregnant. It includes early sexual debut, unprotected sexual activities, inconsistent condom use, high risk partners (injecting drug users), survival sex (sex in exchange for money, drugs, food, or shelter), or sex with a partner who has other partners or more than one partner at a time. Consequently, dangerous sexual behaviour can take on a variety of shapes, from having a lot of partners or investing a lot of time in risky sexual behaviours to engaging in sexual activity while under the influence of drugs or alcohol.

Young adults and teenagers are more vulnerable than adults. Dimbuene et.al. (2014) described risky sexual behaviour as the activity that will increase the probability that a person engaging in sexual activity with another person infected with a sexually transmitted infection will be infected or become pregnant, or make a partner pregnant. Risky sexual behaviour is characterized by different hazardous behaviours such as premarital sex, multiple sexual partners, and unprotected sex which have been reported to end up with unpleasant health outcomes like HIV/AIDS, unwanted pregnancies, and unsafe abortions (Alamrew et al., 2013). Cherie and Berhane (2012) also noted that high school students and young adults are at high risk of contracting HIV due to their risky sexual practices. World Health Organization (2006) listed technological transitions, which make it easier to distribute sexual information from more liberal to more conservative societies as one of the major contributory factors to the high risky sexual behaviour while Graham (2012) highlighted other factors such as peer pressure, unlicensed erotic films, drugs and alcohol abuse.

Studies have revealed a marked increase in the percentage of adolescents who engage in sexual behaviour while attending school. There is general agreement that high-risk sexual behaviour among adolescents puts them at risk for issues with their reproductive health. This is due to physiologic and psychological changes that make people crave sexual activity and take risks, which has a negative impact on sexual and reproductive health indicators such unexpected pregnancies, unsafe abortions, early childbearing, sexually

transmitted illnesses, and AIDS. Adolescents are known for being an adventurous lot, and they frequently engage in risky activities like smoking, drinking, taking drugs, and having unprotected sexual relations in their early years. Due to the abundance of unfiltered information, they are exposed to through a growing wave of westernization, the Internet, and electronic media, behaviours like homosexuality, lesbianism, and sexual orgies are engaged in only for the purpose of experimentation and peer influences. Perhaps this explains why Hall (1904) described adolescence as a time of 'storm and stress. Ivankovich et al., (2013) asserted that sexual transmitted infection (STI) and unplanned pregnancies are in the list of public health problems worldwide and currently on the rise. Understanding the extent to which risky sexual behavior is prevalent among adolescents is crucial in developing effective interventions and policies. Research suggests that a significant proportion of adolescents are involved in risky sexual practices, contributing to an increased risk of unintended pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and HIV/AIDS transmission. However, the exact prevalence rates of risky sexual behavior among adolescents remain unclear due to variations across different populations, cultural norms, and methodological limitations in data collection. An in-depth analysis of the determinants contributing to risky sexual behavior among adolescents is essential for developing targeted interventions. Various factors can influence adolescents' engagement in risky sexual behavior, including individual, interpersonal, and societal factors. Individual determinants may include a lack of knowledge about sexual health, low self-esteem, sensation-seeking behavior, and limited access to sexual health services. Interpersonal determinants may involve peer influences, social norms, family dynamics, and communication patterns. Societal determinants could encompass cultural and religious beliefs, inadequate sexual education curricula, and socioeconomic disparities. It is therefore, on this premise, that this study examines the prevalence and determinants of risky sexual behaviour among students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers East Senatorial District.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Area of the Study

The geographical coverage of this research is restricted to Public Senior Secondary Schools within Rivers East Senatorial District, Nigeria.

Research Design

This study employed two designs, a descriptive cross sectional design and correlational design.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all the students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers East Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 1229 students in senior secondary schools. This sample size was determined using proportionate formula method.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted for the study in three stages.

Stage one: Simple random sampling technique was used to select four Local Government Areas which are: Emohua, Etche, Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt city Local Government Areas by balloting without replacement.

Stage two: simple random sampling techniques was used to select four schools from the four selected Local Government Areas. This was done by balloting without replacement. The selected schools are Emohua: OCSS Rumuewhor, CSS Rumuji, CSS Ndele, and UCHS Ibaa; Etche: GSS Okehi, CSS Isu, CSS Umuechem and GSS Ozuzu; Obio/Akpor: GSS Eneka, CSS Iriebe, CSS Okoro-nu-odu, and CSS Ogbogoro; Port Harcourt city: CSS Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, CSS Amadi-Ama, CSS Abuloma and GSS Rumuodomaya respectively.

Stage three: systematic sampling technique was adopted to select 77 students from 15 of selected senior secondary schools and 74 from one school (because of the population and availability of students) to make up the sample for the study.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: Prevalence and Determinants of Risky Sexual Behaviours among Students (QPDRSBS).

Validity of the Instrument

The designed instrument was validated by three experts in the field of Reproduction Health, Public Health and Measurement and Evaluation.

Reliability of the Instrument

Test-retest method was adopted to enhance instrument reliability. 40 copies of the instrument were administered to students in government owned secondary schools in Eleme and Oyigbo that are homogenous to the study area for a pretest. After two weeks same instrument was given to the same students for post-test. Kuder-Richardson 21 was used to determine the reliability coefficient of 0.79 indicating a positive result. Hence, the instrument was reliable and appropriate and applicable for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher with the help of four assistants administered the questionnaires to the respondents and ensures that they are collected in an interval of two weeks.

Method of Data Analyses

Collected data was analysed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS). Descriptive statistics such as frequencies percentages, means and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Inferential statistical analysis such as regression model was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Prevalence of risky sexual behaviour

SN	Items	Yes Freq %	No Freq %	Decision
1	I have more than one sexual partner	884(71.9)	345(28.1)	High
2	My partner injects drugs before sex	160(13.0)	1069(87.0)	Low
3	I give sex as an exchange for survival	151(12.3)	1078(87.7)	Low
4	I enjoy giving oral sex	396(32.2)	833(67.8)	Low
5	I enjoy receiving oral sex,	77(6.3)	1152(93.7)	Low
6	I enjoy sex without the use of a condom	213(17.3)	1016(82.7)	Low
7	I engage in unprotected anal sex.	65(5.3)	1164(94.7)	Low
8	I get my sexual organs stimulated with hands.	141(11.5)	1088(88.5)	Low
Grand Total		261(21.1)	968(78.8)	Low

Decision: > 50 % High, < 50 Low

Table 1 shows the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was low 21(21.1%).

Table 2: Chi-square test showing significant relationship between peer pressure and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District

Variable	Risky Sexual Behaviour		Total	χ^2 (P-Value) df	Decision
	Yes	No			
	Freq %	Freq %			
Pressured					
No	219(22.0)	776(78.0)	995(100)	157.223	Rejected
Yes	40(17.1)	194(82.9)	234(100)	0.000	
Total	259(21.1)	970(78.9)	1229(100)	1	

***Significant, p<0.05**

The result in table 2 above revealed that there was a significant relationship between peer pressure (X^2 value = 157.223; df =1; p<0.05) and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between peer pressure and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 3: Chi-square test showing significant relationship between sexual orientation and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District

Variable	Risky Sexual Behaviour		Total	χ^2 (P-Value) df	Decision
	Yes	No			
	Freq %	Freq %			
Sexual orientation					
Yes	259(70.2)	110(29.8)	369(100)	760.127	Rejected
No	1(0.1)	859(99.9)	860(100)	0.000	
Total	260(21.1)	969(78.8)	1229(100)	1	

***Significant, p<0.05**

The result in table 3 above revealed that there was a significant relationship between sexual orientation (X^2 value = 760.127; df =1; p<0.05) and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between sexual orientation and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 4: Chi-square test showing significant relationship between parent’s socioeconomic status and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District

Variable	Risky Sexual Behaviour		Total	χ^2 (P-Value) df	Decision
	Yes	No			
	Freq %	Freq %			
Parental socio-economic status					
Low	155(18.0)	705(82.0)	860(100)	164.558	Rejected
High	105(28.4)	264(71.5)	369(100)	0.000	
Total	260(21.1)	969(78.8)	1229(100)	2	

***Significant, p<0.05**

The result in table 4 above revealed that there was a significant relationship between parent’s socioeconomic status (X^2 value = 164.558; df =3; p<0.05) and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between parent’s socioeconomic status and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was rejected.

Table 5: Chi-square test showing significant relationship between belief system and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District

Variable	Risky Sexual Behaviour		Total	χ^2 (P-Value) df	Decision
	Yes	No			
	Freq %	Freq %			
Belief system					
Christian	250(23.7)	805(76.3)	1055(100)	75.366	Rejected
Muslim	0(0.0)	162(100)	162(100)	0.000	
Others	10(83.3)	2(16.7)	12(100)	2	
Total	260(21.2)	969(78.8)	1229(100)		

***Significant, p<0.05**

The result in table 5 above revealed that there was a significant relationship between belief system (X^2 value = 75.366; df =2; p<0.05) and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between belief system and risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was rejected.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings of the study show the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that the prevalence of risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District was low 261(21.1%). This result was expected because of the strong moral requirement associated with the Christian religion that's predominant in the area, also most African cities are known for their family values that promote sexual purity and the societal expectation of good morals from adolescents. This result implies low prevalence of sexual risk behaviours among adolescents in Rivers east senatorial zone. The finding in this study is in line with that of Eyam et al., (2021) with an average prevalence of sexual intercourse at 41.5% among secondary school adolescents in Cross River State, Nigeria. Also in line with the findings of Mengesha and Enguday (2019) showed prevalence of risky sexual behavior among adolescents aged 15-19 years was found to be 17.2%. Also Emmanuel et al., (2020) showed the prevalence of risky sexual behaviors among students was found to be 41% among high school students from Collège Saint André in Kigali, Rwanda. Tadesse et al., (2018) showed the prevalence rate of risky sexual behaviors was reported as 30.5% among among high school and preparatory school students in Mizan Aman Town, Ethiopia.

Concerning risky sexual behaviours, Some identified behaviours are early sexual debut, multiple sexual partners, substance abuse, unprotected sex, visiting commercial sex workers. Tolera et al., (2017) showed 17.07% of high and preparatory school youth in East Wollega, Ethiopia had more than one sexual partner and 11.9% of male students visited commercial sex workers. Durowade et al., (2017) showed the prevalence of early sexual debut was about 11%, the mean age of sexual debut was 13.10 ± 2.82 and the mean number of sexual partners was 2.44 ± 1.99 . Teklemariam, et al., (2018) showed 57.6% of the study participants reported to have sexual intercourse before age of eighteen, 16.3% had more than one sexual partner, 16.7% had sexual intercourse with commercial sex workers and 86.9% reported inconsistent use of condoms, alcohol drinking was reported by 17.2% of the respondents whereas 4.8% said that they chew khat.

The finding of this study does not agree with that of Keto et al., (2020) where 22.7% of the students of Metu town, south western Ethiopia had engaged in sexual activity, of which 61.7% had more than one sexual partner and 58% never used condoms. Noor (2017) showed among among school-going adolescent in Malaysia; those who ever had sex, it was reported that 87.3 percent (95% CI: 84.8, 89.4) of them did not use condom, 16.6 percent (95% CI: 14.0, 19.6) had multiple sexual partners. According to Tadele et al., (2018) in a systematic review and meta-analysis of epidemiology of risky sexual behaviors in college and university students in Ethiopia, the prevalence of risky sexual behavior ranged from 23.3% to 60.9%. The estimated pooled prevalence of risky sexual behaviors among college and university students was 41.62% with 95% CI (36.15, 47.10). Several factors are responsible for the high prevalence of risky sexual behaviour which includes family factors such as poor socioeconomic status of parents, living in rural areas, and polygamous homes, individual factors such as poor knowledge of safe sex practices and the consequences of risky behaviours, societal factors such as cultural norms like early marriage and unbridled quest for wealth.

The findings of the study shows the extent peer pressure determine risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that based on peer pressure of respondents, risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students was more among those who were pressured ($\bar{x} = 2.73 \pm 0.94$), followed by those who were not pressured ($\bar{x} = 2.32 \pm 0.98$) Thus based on peer pressure, risky sexual behaviour were more among those who were pressured. This result was expected as adolescent stage has been noted as the stage people are most susceptible to pressure from peers. This finding supports that of Durowade et al., (2017) which showed having friends who engaged in sexual activities had association with early sexual exposure ($p < 0.05$). Also Tolera et al., (2017) showed being forced by classmates for sex [AOR, 95% CI 7.63(2.36-24.66)] was an independent predictor of risky sexual behaviour. Keto et al., (2020) in their study revealed that peer pressure was a major factor that influenced the students' sexual behaviours and recommended promoting peer education and discussion to protect adolescents from risky sexual behaviours. Birhan, (2019) and Emmanuel et al.,

(2020) identified peer pressure among other factors as influencing factors for risky sexual behaviours. Eze, et. al., (2021) showed 36.0% of unmarried adolescents in Southeast Nigeria had been pressurized by others to have sex. To buttress this, Adimas, et al., (2021) showed peer pressure (AOR=4.86, 95% CI, 2.31-10.22) and permissive type of parenting style (AOR=0.27, 95% CI, 0.10-.70) are factors significantly associated with risky sexual behavior at P- value <0.05. In Obio/akpor local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria, Gabriel-Job et al., (2018) showed peer pressure ($\chi^2 = 17.007$, $P \leq 0.001$) was responsible for early sexual debut. Also Nwigwe and Agbapuonwu (2023) showed some of the factors associated with risky sexual behaviours include: substance abuse, prestige of multiple partners, sexual activity for financial gain, sexual activity for good grades, casual sex partners, peer pressure, gender issues, media, sexual activity to relieve stress, easy access to sex, watching of pornographic. Peer pressure is a potent force responsible for risky sexual behaviour and can be controlled by quality sex education and good parental influence.

The findings of the study shows the extent sexual orientations determine risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that among respondents, risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students was more among those who had sexual orientation (X^2 value = 760.127; df =1; $p < 0.05$), followed by those who had no sexual orientation. Thus based on sexual orientation, risky sexual behaviour were more among those who had sexual orientation. This result was expected because exposure to sexual activities can influence involvement in unsafe sex. The finding of this study is in agreement with Odii et al. (2020) study which found out that risky sexual behaviours among adolescent undergraduate students are embedded in the quality of sex education by parents at early adolescence, as such, unprotected sex and multiple sexual partners were rampant among adolescents who were not exposed to quality sex education at early adolescence. Also a study by Alsubaie (2018) showed most respondents (387, 85.6%) believed that adolescents needed school-based sex education, with 418 (92.3%) citing that sex education was effective and required for protection against STIs and establishing healthy sexual behaviour. According to Tadesse et al. (2018), risky sexual behaviors was associated with discussing the issue of sexuality with family (AOR=0.349; 95% CI: 0.191-0.541), to buttress this point, Bedru, et al. (2022) showed that having no access to information on unsafe sexual practice (AOR=3.60, 95% CI=2.11, 6.13) and poor knowledge of unsafe sexual practice (AOR=4.59, 95% CI=2.630,8.018), were significantly associated with the unsafe sexual practice.

Early sexual debut is associated with risky sexual behaviour due to high sexual orientation at an early age. Karlsen (2019) showed engaging in age disparate relationships was significantly associated with engaging in transactional sex and unprotected sex; at a very young age a significant number of females in the sample was involved in age disparate relationships putting them at risk of contracting HIV early on in life. The similarity in the findings is because sexual orientation is an important factor in controlling risky sexual behaviour, this highlights the need for inculcating age appropriate sex education in our institutions of learning.

The findings of the study shows the extent parent's socioeconomic status determine risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that among respondents, risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students was more among those whose parents socio-economic status was low ($\bar{X} = 2.92 \pm 0.79$), followed by high ($\bar{X} = 2.46 \pm 0.86$). Thus based on parent's socioeconomic status, risky sexual behaviour were more among those whose parents socio-economic status was low. This result was expected as socioeconomic status has been shown to be an important predictor of engagement in risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in the society. This finding is in line with the works of Eyam et al., (2021) which showed 49.4% of the students whose mothers had at most primary education have had sexual exposure compared to 34% of those whose mothers had at least secondary education have had sexual exposure ($\chi^2 = 18.23$; $P = 0.00$). Similarly, students whose parents had unskilled jobs also had a high percentage of sexual exposure ($\chi^2 = 13.6$; $P = 0.00$). Thus socioeconomic status was strongly associated with risky sexual behaviour. Also Mengesha and Enguday (2019) showed factors like poor social support (AOR=5:59, 95% CI: 2.71-11.53), living out of family (AOR=1:93, 95% CI: 1.21-3.07) and experiencing parental neglect (AOR=1:87, 95% CI: 1.18-

2.94) were statistically associated with risky sexual behaviour. According to Birhan, (2019) current living conditions was an influencing factor for risky sexual behaviour, this was buttressed by Tadesse et al. (2018) which showed risky sexual behaviours were associated with issues including being from rural areas (AOR=2.041; 95% CI: 1.224-3.403)

Nnebue et al., (2015) in a study among senior secondary schools students in a military barracks in Nigeria showed low socioeconomic background for both parents and doing income earning jobs were associated with sexual intercourse ($p= 0.008$; $p= 0.021$; $p= 0.000$). Living with single parent is a very strong predictor of ever had sex ($p=0.000$). Also Bedru, et al. (2022) showed that having monthly pocket money (AOR=9.4, 95% CI=5.28, 16.81), parental polygamous marriage type (AOR=5.41, 95% CI=1.55, 18.90) were significantly associated with the unsafe sexual practice. In addition, Olorunsola, et al. (2021) stated that predictors of unsafe sexual behaviour were lower social class (OR: 2.721, Confidence Interval: 1.422-5.308) and conflict- oriented family types (OR= 1.894 C.I: 1.036-3.462). The similarity in the findings may be because socioeconomic status is a strong predictor of risky sexual behaviour. The implication of this finding is the promulgation of better economic policies will have an effect on both parents and their children; young girls would not be coerced into the lifestyle of exchanging sex for gifts. The findings of the study shows the extent belief system determine risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District. The result showed that based on belief system of respondents, risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students were more among Islam ($\bar{X} = 2.62 \pm 0.83$), followed by Christians ($\bar{X} = 2.48 \pm 0.98$), and Traditionalists ($\bar{X} = 1.21 \pm 0.58$). Thus based on belief system, educational status, risky sexual behaviour was more among Islam belief system. This result was expected because Islam allows for multiple partners although within the confines of marriage. The finding of this study agrees with Bedru, et al., (2022) which showed that rare church attendance (AOR=8.8, 95% CI=4.95, 15.73), was significantly associated with the unsafe sexual practice. The finding of the study does not agree with that of Watsi, et al. (2020) which showed muslims were 89% less likely to engage in risky sexual behaviours than christians ($p=0.032$), this may be due to other factors such as socioeconomic status, knowledge of safe sex practices and access to good health care services. Religion is an important factor in controlling risky sexual behaviours as shown by Tolera et al., (2017) which concluded that risky sexual behaviour of school youth reduced by high family connectedness alongside attending religious services regularly and Alsubaie (2018) where majority (422, 93.2%) believed that religion played a crucial role in discouraging sexual behavioural problems. This was buttressed by the study of Ugoji (2008) which indicated that there was a significant relationship between risky sexual behaviour and emotional intelligence, self-esteem, media and religiosity. The joint effect of emotional intelligence, self-esteem, media and religiosity on risky sexual behaviour was significant ($F(4,295) = 56.354$; $R = 0.667$, $R^2 = 0.445$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.430$; $p < 0.05$). About 43% of the variation was accounted for by the independent variables and the most potent being religiosity. The implication of this study is religious leaders have an important role to play in the control of risky sexual behaviours as they help form the belief system of the community and shape their mindsets on life issues, therefore there should be emphasis on the message of morality to adolescents and the need to avoid premarital sex.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that there is low prevalence of risky sexual behaviour and factors that determine risky sexual behaviour include, peer pressure, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status of parents and belief system. There was significant difference in risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Rivers East Senatorial District based on the above listed factors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- The government through the Ministry of Education should implement a comprehensive sex education curriculum that covers topics such as reproductive health, contraception, sexually transmitted

infections (STIs), and consent. The curriculum should be age-appropriate, culturally sensitive, and address the specific needs of the students in Rivers State.

- The ministry of education should conduct training programs for teachers to equip them with the knowledge and skills to effectively deliver sex education with emphasis on the importance of creating a safe and non-judgmental space for students to ask questions and seek guidance.
- Non-governmental organizations should foster collaboration between schools and local communities to promote awareness and understanding of the importance of sex education. Organize workshops for parents to enhance their communication skills with their children on sexual health matters.
- School principals should establish peer education programs where older students act as mentors and share accurate information about sexual health with their peers. Peer education can create a supportive environment for open discussions and reduce stigma surrounding sexual health topics.
- The state ministry of health should provide improved access to youth-friendly reproductive health services within or near schools and ensuring that students have access to confidential counselling, contraceptives, and STI testing, with a focus on eliminating barriers such as stigma and cost.

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